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Observational Fieldwork Research Guide

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Executive Summary

Observational fieldwork research is a qualitative method that explores human behaviour through the observation of individuals and groups. The most common form of this method is natural observation, in which subjects are observed in their natural environments. Unlike other techniques (e.g., surveys or interviews) that rely on self-reported information, observational research captures actual behaviours, providing valuable insights into what people do rather than what they claim to do. Still, it is often combined with other methods or used as a preliminary step. With roots in anthropology and sociology, natural observation involves researchers immersing themselves in the study setting, where they may take on various roles ranging from passive observers to active participants, carefully documenting their observations through detailed field notes. Although observational research offers a unique perspective on human behaviour, it does present certain challenges. It can be time-consuming, and its subjective nature may lead to differing interpretations among researchers.

This guide offers a concise overview of observational research, emphasising its key features. It covers when and where to conduct observations, what to observe, and what to document. In addition, the guide discusses the advantages and disadvantages of this research method, along with critical ethical considerations. It outlines the essential steps in the research process and rounds off with suggestions for further reading. It is important to note that this guide does not specifically concentrate on the observational research activities that may occur within INSPIRE. Instead, it offers a broader perspective that could be useful in various contexts.

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1. The basics of observational fieldwork research

1.1 Conceptual delineation

1.1.1 Observation methods

Observation methods are a type of methodology used in **descriptive research**. They involve systematically recording the behavioural patterns of people, objects, events, and (human) artifacts (e.g., social media posts) to gather information about phenomena of interest. Notably, observation focuses on **what people do** rather than just what they say or what they say they do (Walsh, 2020). A central distinction in observation methods is between natural and contrived observation. Natural observation comprises observing behaviour in its natural setting(s), while contrived observation occurs in an artificial environment, such as a laboratory (Malhotra, 2019). This guide concentrates on **natural observation**.

The core premise behind natural observation is that by spending time alongside the members of a group or a community, researchers are in a better position to observe and even partake in a wide variety of situations as they unfold **in their natural settings**, *in situ*. These experiences allow researchers to reconcile what the subjects might say (e.g., in interviews) and what they actually do (Franco & Yang, 2021).

Figure 1: Observation in a nutshell

1.1.2 Distinctions of (natural) observation methods

Within natural observation, **several distinctions** can be made, including covert vs. undisguised, structured vs. unstructured, and active vs. passive observation. The most prevalent distinction or use of terms, however, is between non-participant and participant observation (Sofield & Marafa, 2019).

Non-participant observation, often referred to as “pure observation” or “passive observation”, implies no intervention by field researchers. In contrast, participant observation entails researchers actively engaging with the subjects. Interestingly, although the element of participation might be seen as distracting, participant observation seeks to preserve the naturalness of the research encounter and minimise the disruption that may arise from the researchers’ presence in the field (Walsh, 2020). Some scholars further identify three interactive modes of participation: moderate (i.e., minimal membership), active (i.e., participation in as many events as possible within a group or community),

and complete (i.e., becoming a full member of the group, often referred to as “going native”) (Wilson, 2005; Sofield & Marafa, 2019) (see Table 1 for an overview and the main associated constraints). It is important to note, though, that even in the case of passive observation, the researcher-observer

might still become a member of the “dramatis personae”¹ of a group or a scene of action and, as such, turn into a carrier of the group or scene characteristics (Schostak, 2010).

Finally, it can be mentioned that **non-participatory** forms often centre on factual descriptions, such as how often events occur, how many participants are involved, and who attended. As a result, these forms tend to be more **structured**. In contrast, participatory forms typically embrace a more unstructured approach, allowing for greater flexibility and creativity in gathering insights (Guest et al., 2013).

Table 1. Observation modes along the “non-participant – participant” continuum

Type	Level of researchers’ involvement	Core constraints for researchers
Non-participatory / passive / pure	Researchers assume a bystander role	It might be hard to establish rapport and immerse themselves in the field
Moderate	Researchers try to strike a balance between “insider” and “outsider” roles	It might not be easy to attain a balanced blend of involvement and detachment
Active	Researchers become active members of a group or a community	Researchers might struggle to maintain an adequate level of objectivity
Complete	Researchers integrate into the study population / “go native”	Researchers might lose all objectivity, which could compromise the research integrity

Note: Based on Sofield and Marafa (2019), and Walsh (2020)

1.1.3 Participant observation and ethnography

Observation methods have deep **roots in ethnographic traditions**. Strikingly, some scholars use the terms “participant observation” and “ethnography” **interchangeably** (Fine, 2015). While these concepts are closely related, they have distinct meanings. Participant observation is a fundamental method often employed by ethnographers. On the contrary, **ethnography** is not conceived or treated as a unitary research method but rather as a **broader research approach** for studying people, communities, and cultures in their local settings. As such, it routinely integrates additional methods like interviews and surveys (Walsh, 2020). Interestingly, as we discuss in Section 1.2, in applied research, participant observation is also frequently combined with other qualitative methods, such as interviews and focus groups (Malhotra, 2019), or serves as valuable preparatory groundwork for questionnaire-based methods like surveys (Liu et al., 2024).

The historical foundations of ethnography can be traced back to classical antiquity, particularly to the writings of **Herodotus** (Robben & Sluka, 2015). The method of participant observation developed from the accounts of **adventurers** and **missionaries**, and later, it was adopted by the first **anthropologists** (Schostak, 2010). In the 1920s, **sociologists** began to embrace this approach; the Department of Sociology at the University of Chicago was the first to send sociologists into the field. They produced ethnographies that explored various aspects of the ethnically, occupationally, and socially diverse urban landscape of Chicago through participant observation (Wilson, 2005; Fine, 2015). Today,

¹ People who figure prominently in something, such as an event.

participant observation is utilised across various disciplines to gain insights into the lives of individuals, groups, and communities (Liu et al., 2023).

1.2 Key features of natural observation

1.2.1 Why and which type(s)?

As has been implied above and as outlined by Guest et al. (2013), the **five core reasons** behind choosing natural observation methods are the following:

1. To capture observed behaviour within its physical context.
2. To witness the behaviour of interest as it occurs.
3. To avoid potential biases associated with self-reported data.
4. To reduce reporting biases (e.g., using global standards that may not align with local contexts).
5. To complement other research methods or to identify topics for further inquiry.

Is natural observation a standalone method? As the fifth reason suggests, observation is often used **in conjunction with** other data collection techniques, particularly interviews and focus groups, or as a **precursor** to other methods (Wilson, 2005; Malhotra, 2019). Therefore, research teams might have to consider how to effectively **combine** observation with **complementary** techniques and methods that may be easier to implement or how observation **might lay the groundwork** for further data collection (Fetterman, 2015; Liu et al., 2023).

As for the actual types of natural observation, the choice typically depends on the research questions the teams aim to address, as well as the strategies selected to tackle these questions. To illustrate, research teams generally start by **answering specific questions**, such as their research goals, how to achieve them, what locations to select, and which individuals and behaviours to focus on, before determining the appropriate types of observation methods. Not unexpectedly, it is common for research teams to **blend** different types of natural observation (Sanjek, 2015), and for researchers to **assume different roles simultaneously** (e.g., the role of outsider and insider) (Walsh, 2020).

1.2.2 Where?

As has been emphasised above, natural observation always takes place in the **natural setting(s)** occupied by members of a group or a community. This means that researchers engage with the subjects in their own settings rather than asking them to come to a different location for the study (Mack et al., 2005). Natural scenery often includes **public** or **semi-public** settings such as playgrounds, work sites, libraries, airports, transportation vehicles, shopping malls, hospitals, village plazas, stores, political rallies, and online chat rooms (Guest et al., 2013).

The exact locations to select need to be **relevant to the research questions** (Wilson, 2005). In rural contexts, these locations often pertain to agricultural activities (e.g., farming, herding), social activities (e.g., lineage events like weddings, funerals, local festivals, celebrations for birthdays), and activities held in public spaces (e.g., schools, village health centres, public sports facilities) (Liu et al., 2024). In studies focusing on social exclusion, locations of interest customarily include places where social initiatives are deployed, like soup kitchens, food banks, and social retail shops (Gracia-Arnaiz, 2022). In a similar vein, in research projects centred on social exclusion in rural areas, it can be expected that physical facilities of social services, community centres, and the premises of local social economy organizations may be chosen as potential settings for exploration.

Additionally, researchers frequently need to define specific **observation areas or spaces within these settings** to determine where to channel their observations, especially when the observation method is intended to be passive and structured (Gamberini et al., 2013).

When considering **actual research venues**, how do research teams decide? The selection depends on the research objectives and the selection of samples (e.g., who, where, what) that will assist research teams in achieving their goals (Sanjek, 2015). If research teams have **prior knowledge** about the individuals, behaviours, or events they wish to study, they can identify at least some locations where they can observe these (Guest et al., 2013). Unsurprisingly, researchers’ personal connections and preferences influence the selection process. However, they must still provide **justification for their choices** based on an underlying theory or conceptual framework steering their field research (Sanjek, 2015).

Noticeably, the **ideal locations** for researching a problem are **not always available**. In such cases, researchers acknowledge and document the study’s limitations from the onset. If feasible, they **adjust** the focus of their investigation to align with the available sites (Fetterman, 2015). It is generally advisable to conduct some **preliminary research** on the study areas before getting there (Franco & Yang, 2021). Therefore, it is important to adhere to the **location observation “mantra”** presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The location observation "mantra"

1.2.3 When and for how long?

When conducting observational research, it is ideal for researchers to reside in the community or the location of a group for six months to a year or even longer. This **extended presence** allows them to observe and document behavioural patterns over time, **helping them to internalise** the fundamental beliefs, fears, hopes, and expectations of the people they are studying. However, in practical situations, especially in applied research, **budget constraints** and **time limitations** often prevent researchers from engaging in long-term residence (Fetterman, 2015).

The duration of **each observation session** varies based on the setting, activity, and population being studied. Researchers may spend an hour, an afternoon, or several afternoons in a specific environment. The ideal timing for scheduling observation sessions depends on what, who, and where the researchers need to focus their observations (Guest et al., 2013).

1.2.4 With whom?

The actual observation can be conducted **individually, in pairs, or in teams**, depending on what is most suitable for the specific locations and topics being studied. When deciding on the best arrangement, factors such as age, gender, physical appearance, ethnicity, personality, and linguistic abilities of the data collectors are often taken into account. The goal is to gather data in the **least intrusive** and **most effective** way possible, considering the research objectives, the unique characteristics of the studied population, and the local context. One approach when the research

team consists of several members is to have them **disperse** to various locations either individually, in pairs, or in small groups to conduct observations aimed at addressing specific questions and then **reconvene** to compare their notes (Mack et al., 2005).

1.2.5 What to observe?

The **range of observations** during observational research can be quite **diverse**. Ultimately, it is determined by the research objectives, the selection of samples, and any practical limitations. However, there are general categories that are commonly observed, which are outlined in Table 2 below.

Table 2. What to observe in general

Category	Elements to observe
Appearance	Clothing, age, gender, physical appearance, and anything that might indicate membership in groups or in subpopulations of interest
Verbal behaviour	Who speaks to whom, the duration of interactions, who initiates conversations, the languages or dialects used, and the tone of voice employed
Physical behaviour	What people do, who is responsible for specific tasks, the interactions that occur, those who remain uninvolved, and what people’s behaviours indicate about their feelings toward one another
Human traffic	How many people enter, leave, and spend time at the observation site, the duration of their visits, their frequency of return, whether they are alone or accompanied
Personal space	The proximity of individuals to each other, and what people’s preferences concerning personal space suggest about their relationships
People who stand out	Identification of individuals who attract significant attention from others, whether they seem to be strangers or well-known by others present

Note: Based on Mack et al. (2005)

Notably, the **flexibility** of observation methods provides research teams with **considerable freedom** regarding what to observe during their studies. The choice of what to observe also depends on the **level of structure**. As we have emphasised above, the level should **align with the research objectives**. Additionally, what to observe might correspond with the **stage of learning** the research is intended to illuminate. For instance, less structure is necessary for broad, exploratory, and early-stage research and more structure for focused, applied studies that are intended to provide additional depth or confirmation on topics where a lot is already known (Guest et al., 2013).

1.2.6 How and what to document?

The researchers must not only observe activities but also record the material in what is known as **“field notes”**. These documents serve as evidence for the observations made (Fine, 2015). Field notes capture the researchers’ observations, conversations, interactions, and experiences, along with their reflections on their role and influence within the community and its members (Wilson, 2005). Essentially, they are written or digital records of what researchers saw, heard, felt, and even affected during the observation period (Guest et al., 2013).

Field notes can be written in a paper or electronic notebook² either discreetly **during** an observation or **after** the activity has concluded, depending on the researchers' level of participation and the context. Regardless of when they are written, it is important to expand on these notes as soon as possible to preserve the details before memory fades (Mack et al., 2005). To prepare for more comprehensive field notes, researchers often start with "**scratch notes**", which are brief jottings made during the sessions. These scratch notes serve as a foundation for developing the full written field notes later (Sanjek, 2015).

However, during certain events, researchers may need to focus their attention on what is happening in **real time**, making it difficult to even take scratch notes. In some situations, note-taking may not even be appropriate. For example, as Schostak (2010) illustrates, taking notes in a gang setting would likely be viewed as unnatural, whereas doing so in a classroom is completely acceptable. In summary, the decision to take notes - whether in the form of scratch notes or fuller field notes - depends on the specific circumstances of the observation.

As anticipated, field notes in their "scratch" form are often viewed as **messy**. They may contain emotional responses, incomplete analyses, unresolved questions, interpretations that are not fully developed, or even admissions of mistakes. In academic research, it is rare to come across samples of these rough notes. The absence of published examples can lead to anxiety for inexperienced researchers who lack a reference for their early attempts. By the time field notes are shared publicly, they have typically been reorganised and rephrased (Walsh, 2020). Therefore, while **clarity**, **concision**, and **completeness** are essential in note-taking, **style is not a major focus** (Fetterman, 2015).

Finally, the field notes in their final form are usually kept in **chronological** order and may be **indexed** separately by actor and topic. Additionally, researchers conducting field observations often create records first organised by categories such as topic, person, or other classifications, and then order them chronologically (Sanjek, 2015).

1.2.7 Advantages

Admittedly, observational methods offer several distinct advantages, most of which have been implied above. Perhaps the most important pros are the following:

- **Validity:** One of the greatest benefits of observational methods is their ability to measure actual behaviour rather than relying on self-reported, intended, or assumed behaviour (Malhotra, 2019). As a result, field observational research tends to maximise validity, which refers to the extent to which scientific observations accurately measure what they are intended to measure (Sanjek, 2015). Besides, as highlighted at the beginning of this guide, observation focuses on recording what people do rather than only what they say or claim to do. Still, it can be pointed out that observational research records people's manifest behaviours without necessarily unveiling their underlying motivations, feelings, or preferences (Malhotra, 2019).
- **Openness:** Observational research is highly receptive to emerging data, with minimal instrument bias. This approach can reveal a wealth of previously unknown information to researchers (Guest et al., 2013). Furthermore, it reduces the risk of reporting bias. By immersing themselves in the study environment, researchers can avoid imposing preconceived notions or frameworks that may not be suitable for the specific contexts they study (Schostak, 2010). Nonetheless, as implied in section 1.2.5, there is a trade-off between openness and structure. While a structured approach

² In addition to using field notebooks, audio and video recordings can be employed to record individuals, behaviours, and events (Wilson, 2005).

can ease data collection and analysis, it may also constrain the openness of the research and what field researchers can observe (Guest et al., 2013).

- **Richness:** In contrast to many research techniques that do not involve personal witnessing, observational methods provide the opportunity to collect rich and detailed data (Fine, 2015).

1.2.8 Disadvantages

Observational methods offer several advantages, but they also have significant disadvantages. Some of the main challenges associated with these methods include the following:

- **Time:** Observational research is very labour-intensive. It requires the researcher to be present in the observed social setting for extended periods to capture and understand the full range of activities. This level of commitment is often impractical for most applied research studies (Mack et al., 2005).
- **Reliability:** Since observational research often focuses on a specific location, scene, or group, there is a question of whether two researchers observing similar social contexts will arrive at the same conclusions. Differences in their perspectives upon entering the field, as well as variations in their experiences during the observation, can lead to greatly differing conclusions (Fine, 2015).
- **Generalisability:** Even if we acknowledge the validity of analysing a single setting, on what basis can we extend our findings beyond that specific context? How far can we apply our conclusions? Do the results apply only to one situation at a particular moment, or can they be generalised to other settings? In essence, the legitimacy of generalisability will always pose challenges in observational research (Malhotra, 2019).

Special attention might be given to the so-called **Hawthorne effect**, also known as the **observer effect**. The term originates from a study³ conducted on worker productivity at the Hawthorne Electrical Works near Chicago and represents the propensity to change one's behaviour in relation to the awareness of being observed (Zhong and House, 2012). Essentially, people often put forth their best behaviour when they are aware of being observed (Baxter et al., 2015). Thus, the Hawthorne effect can be a significant source of error, as it may lead to changes in behaviour during observations (Zhong and House, 2012). Nevertheless, there are ways to mitigate the issue. One common solution is to expand the observation period, as the Hawthorne effect typically decreases over time. Initially, individuals may alter their behaviour due to the presence of an observer, but as they become more comfortable and develop a rapport with the researcher, their behaviour turns out to be more authentic. Therefore, the longer researchers spend observing people, the less pronounced the observer effect will be. If extending the observation period is not feasible, researchers could consider excluding the initial observation interval from their analysis, as that is when people are more likely to mask their genuine behaviour (Baxter et al., 2015).

³ The Hawthorne studies were originally intended to explore how the physical work environment, such as changes in lighting, could affect worker productivity. Interestingly, the results revealed an unexpected conclusion: social relations, particularly the presence of observer-supervisors, played a more significant role in shaping organizational outcomes than the physical environment itself (Zhong and House, 2012).

1.2.9 Ethical considerations

Although all forms of research involving human subjects raise ethical concerns, observational research presents a wide range of ethical challenges due to the complex interpersonal dynamics involved. Three central ethical issues are commonly found in observational research:

- **Deception:** When conducting observational research, researchers often need to be discreet about their identities and intentions to avoid disrupting normal activities. However, they must also be transparent enough so that the individuals they observe or interact with do not feel that their privacy is being compromised (Guest et al., 2013). In some instances, researchers may not disclose their research agenda, such as when they pose as a customer in a store or as a potential member of a political organisation. These cases can create genuine ethical dilemmas, as a certain level of deception is inherent in the data collection process (Malhotra, 2019).
- **Informed consent:** Other methods, like surveys and interviews, often draw upon written information sheets and consent forms, which are well-established techniques in the social sciences and are easily demonstrated to an ethics committee. However, should observational researchers also be required to obtain informed consent from their subjects? Additionally, it is not so easy to know how much information will be necessary for informed consent, especially when researchers may not fully anticipate which issues will become central to their observations (Walsh, 2020).
- **Confidentiality:** Like in most methods, it is essential for observational researchers to commit to protecting the identities of the individuals they observe or interact with, even in informal settings. Maintaining confidentiality means ensuring that specific individuals cannot be linked to the data they provide. Still, maintaining this confidentiality can be challenging, as field notes may contain descriptions of actions or statements that others present in the same scene could recognise (Fine, 2015).

The fundamental ethical guideline for conducting observational research is to **ensure that no harm is done** to the observed group or community and its members (Wilson, 2005). Researchers must, at a minimum, **avoid disclosing personal details** that could reveal the identities of individuals involved in the study. In some cases, this may **even mean not publishing certain pieces** of information gathered during the research (Mack et al., 2005). Other essential ethical standards include maintaining **honesty** and ensuring **reciprocity**. Reciprocity, at its core, involves researchers answering truthfully any questions posed by the group or community members (Fetterman, 2015). Finally, to **determine the necessary type of informed consent**, researchers can consider three questions recommended by Guest et al. (2013): a) How public or private will the observation venues be? b) What type of data will be collected? and, c) How will the researchers position themselves?

2. Key steps

2.1 Step 1: Craft the “Observational Research Protocol”

The initial step in observational research is to create a comprehensive “Observational Research Protocol”. This protocol should outline seven key elements that are crucial for ensuring clarity and effectiveness. By thoroughly addressing each of these components, a clear framework that guides the data collection process from beginning to end will have been established. More specifically:

1. **Review your research objectives and questions, as well as your conceptualisation:**
 - Clearly define the purpose of your research and the specific questions you plan to address through observational research.

- Ensure that you have examined your theoretical framework, if applicable.
2. **Select appropriate observation methods:**
 - Consider the five core reasons for choosing natural observation, namely capturing behaviour within its natural context, witnessing behaviour as it occurs, avoiding biases associated with self-reported data, reducing reporting biases, and complementing other research methods.
 - Determine the most suitable types of observation (e.g., participant, passive, any combinations) based on your research questions, theorisation, possible venues, and potential subjects.
 3. **Choose observation locations (after following the location observation “mantra”):**
 - Study the “study area” in its entirety (e.g., places, infrastructure, people, services, customs) and in advance.
 - Select specific natural settings relevant to your research (e.g., public spaces, workplaces).
 - Consider factors like accessibility, safety, and ethical implications.
 - Justify your location choices based on your research objectives, theoretical framework, and practical constraints.
 4. **Determine observation timing and duration:**
 - Plan the duration of each observation session based on the setting, activity, and target population.
 - Consider the feasibility of long-term observation (e.g., if budget and time constraints allow).
 - Schedule observation sessions strategically to ensure that you capture relevant behaviours.
 5. **Plan observation teams:**
 - Decide on the optimal team size and composition (individual, pairs, or larger teams).
 - Take into account the observers’ age, gender, ethnicity, and language skills.
 - Ensure the team is well-equipped to collect data in a non-intrusive and effective manner.
 6. **Determine what to observe:**
 - Identify key elements to focus on (e.g., appearance, verbal behaviour, physical behaviour, human traffic, personal space).
 - Tailor the level of observation structure to your research objectives and the stage of learning.
 7. **Develop a system for documenting observations:**
 - Decide how you will utilise field notes to record observations, conversations, interactions, and reflections.
 - Consider using scratch notes for initial jottings and expand on them later.
 - Explore the use of audio and video recordings when appropriate.
 - Determine how you will keep your notes. The standard practice is to maintain them in chronological order and then index them by actor and topic for easier reference.

2.2 Step 2: Fieldwork entry

The second step in observational research involves developing a plan to gain access to the relevant settings. Here is what you may do:

1. **Request and receive ethical clearance from the pertinent Ethical Committee:** To determine what type of informed consent you may need in the observational research, answer the three questions identified above: a) How public or private will the observation venues be? b) What type

of data will be collected? and, c) How will you present/position yourself to the subjects of observation? To answer these questions, consult the Observational Research Protocol first.

2. **If possible, identify and liaise with key informants:** Key informants are local individuals who can provide valuable information about the community or specific groups of interest. They can help you gain a quick understanding of the study population and the cultural environment. Key informants can also facilitate your access to various resources, populations, organisations, and gatekeepers. For instance, consulting with service providers who have experience working with vulnerable populations, such as health practitioners and social workers, can be beneficial in assessing necessary precautions. In addition, key informants can help you make connections between phenomena that may not be obvious to someone unfamiliar with the study area. While researchers often meet such individuals by chance at a field site, it is advisable to identify potential key informants in advance whenever possible.
3. **Prepare a clear and concise self-introduction:** Have an honest version ready that is easy to understand and appropriate for the local context. Avoid any statements that may raise concerns or offend the people you are addressing. It is also essential to practice your self-introduction, as you may need to explain the purpose of your presence in various situations. Be sure to rehearse the self-introduction text thoroughly.
4. **Craft an action plan:** Transform the Observational Research Protocol into a daily or weekly action plan, based on how long you plan to conduct your observations. Use a calendar format and be prepared for potential setbacks that may require you to update the plan regularly.
5. **Create an exit plan:** Exiting the study area is a crucial stage in fieldwork, especially when the observation is participatory. While it may not be necessary, it can be beneficial to proactively consider the potential impacts of your departure and plan some actions (e.g., sending thank-you letters, giving small gifts, hosting celebratory meals).

2.3 Step 3: Fieldwork

The third step in observational research relates to the “moment of truth”. Once you have settled in the area of interest, simply walk into the observation venues and consider the following:

1. **Trust the process:** If you have a thorough Observational Research Protocol and a corresponding action plan, utilise them to their fullest potential.
2. **Position yourself appropriately:** Make sure to have practiced your self-introduction. Depending on the level of structure in the situation, adopt a suitable role, whether passive or more active. Keep in mind that you may need to assume multiple roles at once or switch between them during the same session. However, try to avoid becoming too immersed in the environment you are studying. Becoming overly involved, either unintentionally or intentionally, could negatively impact the quality of your observations.
3. **Observe without interpreting:** Capture the moment by mentally and physically recording what you see, hear, and experience in specific locations and under particular conditions. It is crucial to distinguish between your observations and your expectations or interpretations. In other words, focus on what is actually happening rather than what you expect to see, and ensure that your

expectations do not influence your observations. Moreover, always be mindful of ethical considerations and respect the privacy of individuals.

4. **Note-taking:** Before you start taking notes, remember that it is more important to focus on your observations than on writing them down. However, the sooner you record your observations, the more complete and accurate they will be. Here are some practical tips to enhance your note-taking:
 - Start with “scratch notes” to jot down initial reactions.
 - Use shorthand and keywords to speed up the process.
 - Leave space on the notebook pages to expand your notes later.
 - Schedule time after the observation session to elaborate on your notes.
 - Choose a notebook that will not distract or discomfort the subjects (e.g., using a mobile phone for note-taking might be preferable in certain situations).

5. **Acknowledge the tone:** In line with point 3, it is preferable to use a neutral tone when expanding on your notes. Nevertheless, you may also want to document your feelings too. Therefore, it is important to acknowledge the tone of your notes if you plan to adopt a more subjective style. Here is a short example comparing a subjective summary to a neutral summary of a researcher conducting observation in a nursing home:
 - *Subjective description:* The observation session took place in the common room of the nursing home from 10.00 AM to 11.00 AM. During this time, it was heartening to see the residents engaging in various ways, reflecting their unique mobility and cognitive abilities. Some individuals needed a helping hand to move around, while others confidently navigated on their own. The atmosphere was filled with meaningful social interactions, from intimate group conversations to enthusiastic participation in organised activities like card games, allowing residents to connect and spread joy among one another. Additionally, some residents enjoyed quieter moments, such as reading or watching television.
 - *Neutral description:* The observation session took place in the common room of the nursing home from 10.00 AM to 11.00 AM. Residents demonstrated varying levels of mobility and cognitive abilities. Some required assistance with movement, while others were more independent. Social interactions were observed, including small group conversations and participation in organised activities such as card games. Additionally, solitary activities, like reading or watching television, were also noted.

6. **Exit with style:** Review your exit plan and follow it accordingly. At the very least, express your gratitude to those who assisted you. Additionally, be sure to create a contact file, as you may need to reach out to some of your research subjects during data analysis.

7. **Data management:** After expanding your notes, save them electronically and organise them according to the format agreed upon by your research team (e.g., by providing descriptions based on each setting and using an indexing system). If you have used a notebook, ensure it is stored in a secure location.

3. Further reading

3.1 Rural context

Paper 1

Liu, Q., Liu, Z., Yu, Z., & Zhao, P. (2023). The living environment and intra-village activity-travel: A conceptual framework based on participant observation in Guangdong, China. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 99, 121-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.03.006>

3.2 Rural context and social exclusion

Paper 2

Liu, Q., Ma, T., & Liu, Z. (2024). Reconceptualising transport-related social exclusion in rural China. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 118, Article 103929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2024.103929>

3.3 Social exclusion and vulnerable groups

Paper 3

Gracia-Arnaiz, M. (2022). The precarisation of daily life in Spain: Austerity, social policy and food insecurity. *Appetite*, 171, Article 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2021.105906>

3.4 Structured observations and vulnerable groups

Paper 4

Nosowska, G., McKee, K., & Dahlberg, L. (2014). Using structured observation and content analysis to explore the presence of older people in public fora in developing countries. *Journal of Aging Research*, Article 860612. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/860612>

4. References and declarations

4.1 Reference list

- Baxter, K., Courage, C., & Caine, K. (2015). *Understanding your users. A practical guide to user research methods. A volume in interactive technologies*. Elsevier (2nd ed). ISBN 978-0-12-800232-2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2013-0-13611-2>
- Fetterman, D. A. (2015). Ethnography in applied social research. In J. D. Wright, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 184-191). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.10508-2>
- Fine, G. A. (2015). Participant observation. In J. D. Wright, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 178-183). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.44041-9>
- Franco, P., & Yang, Y. N. (2021). Exiting fieldwork “with grace”: Reflections on the unintended consequences of participant observation and researcher-participant relationships. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 24(3), 358-374. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QMR-07-2020-0094>
- Gamberini, L., Spagnolli, A., Miotto, A., Ferrari, E., Corradi, N., & Furlan, S. (2013). Passengers’ activities during short trips on the London Underground. *Transportation*, 40, 251-268. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-012-9419-4>
- Gracia-Arnaiz, M. (2022). The precarisation of daily life in Spain: Austerity, social policy and food insecurity. *Appetite*, 171, Article 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2021.105906>
- Guest, G., Namey, E. E., & Mitchell, M. L. (2013). *Collecting qualitative data: A field manual for applied research*. SAGE publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506374680>
- Liu, Q., Liu, Z., Yu, Z., & Zhao, P. (2023). The living environment and intra-village activity-travel: A conceptual framework based on participant observation in Guangdong, China. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 99, 121-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.03.006>
- Liu, Q., Ma, T., & Liu, Z. (2024). Reconceptualising transport-related social exclusion in rural China. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 118, Article 103929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2024.103929>
- Mack, N., Woodson, C., MacQueen, K., Guest, G., & Namey, E. (2005). *Qualitative research methods: A data collector’s field guide*. Family Health International. ISBN 0-939704-98-6
- Malhotra, N.K. (2019). *Marketing research: An applied orientation*. Pearson Education (7th ed.). ISBN 978-1292265636
- Robben, A. C. G. M., & Sluka, J. A. (2015). Ethnography. In J. D. Wright, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 530-534). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.12065-3>
- Sanjek, R. (2015). Field observational research in anthropology and sociology. In J. D. Wright, *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 178-183). Elsevier. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.44026-2>

- Schostak, J. F. (2010). Qualitative research: Participant observation. In E. Baker, B. McGaw, & P. Peterson (Eds.), *International Encyclopedia of Education* (3rd ed., pp. 442-448). Elsevier. ISBN 0-08-044893-3.
- Sofield, T. H. B., Marafa, L. M. (2019). Revitalizing fieldtrips in tourism: Visual anthropology, photo elicitation, rapid appraisal, participant observation and Habermas. *Tourism Management*, 75, 522-546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2019.04.007>
- Walch, K. (2020). Participant observation. In A. Kobayashi (Ed.), *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography* (2nd ed., pp. 39-42). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102295-5.10205-7>
- Wilson, T. D. (2005). Participant observation. In K. Kempf-Leonard (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Social Measurement*, (Volume 3, pp. 19-24). Elsevier.
- Zhong, C.-B., & House, J. (2012). Hawthorne revisited: Organizational implications of the physical work environment. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 32, 3-22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2012.10.004>

4.2 Declarations

Declaration of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Writing Process: The author utilised “Grammarly” to improve the overall quality of the language used throughout the document. This tool assisted in detecting grammatical errors, indicating alternative word choices, and refining sentence structure. After using this tool, the author performed an elaborate review and made additional edits to ensure that the content not only met high linguistic standards but also conveyed the intended messages effectively. Ultimately, the author takes full responsibility for the final content.

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